

Evaluation of Hormonal and Histological Changes in the Reproductive System of Mice in Females and Males after Meperidine Administration

Rusul Abdulhameed Kadhim ✉

*Department of Nursing Techniques, Kut Technical Institute,
Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq*

Dhakam Mohammed Abbas ✉

*Department of Medical Laboratory Techniques, Kut Technical Institute,
Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq*

Murtadha Abdulhamid Kadhim

*Department of Medical Laboratory Techniques,
Al-Kut University College, Wasit, Iraq*

Khalied Yassen Zakair

*Department of Medical Laboratory Techniques, Kut Technical Institute,
Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq*

Article History:

Received: 28.07.20254 Revised: 15.08.2025 Accepted: 20.08.2025 Published: 24.08.2025

Abstract

Background: Meperidine is one of the synthetic opioid analgesics regularly given as a prescription after surgery. **Objective:** This study aims to investigate the differential effects of meperidine on the reproductive systems of female and male mice. **Methods:** The study sample was 40 mice. After 14 days, the animals were left for mating. The experiment was divided into two groups: T1, the control animals (n = 20, male and female) were injected (1 ml/day) with distilled water intramuscularly, and T2, the meperidine treatment (n = 20, male and female) was administered (25 mg/kg/day). After 11 weeks, the blood samples were collected for laboratory tests. To perform histological examination, all animals were slaughtered. **Result:** The results showed a significant decrease in the FSH, LH, estrogen and progesterone in the females treated. The testosterone, LH, and FSH levels significantly decreased, whereas prolactin levels were highly significant in the males of the treated group compared to the control group. Histopathological findings of the ovary revealed congested tissues and hyperplasia in the endometrium with inflammatory cell infiltration and germ cell degeneration in testicular tissues. **Conclusion:** In conclusion, this research proved the direct effect of meperidine on the levels of gonadotropins (LH and FSH) and sex hormones (testosterone in males and estrogen in females). Meperidine has an important role on fertility in female mice, in contrast to male mice and body weight.

Keywords: *Meperidine, Reproductive system, Fertility.*

Suggested citation: Kadhim, R.A., Abbas, D.M., Kadhim, M.A., & Zakair, K.Y. (2025). Evaluation of Hormonal and Histological Changes in the Reproductive System of Mice in Females and Males after Meperidine Administration. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(5), 56-65. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(5\).07](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(5).07)

Introduction

Meperidine is an analgesic, sedative drug and one type of opioid agonist used after surgery and childbirth. Chemically, meperidine has a structure similar to local anaesthetics. Meperidine is a synthetic analgesic under the phenylpiperidine group used for intra-articular analgesia, epidural analgesia, and peripheral nerve blocks (Yilmaz, et al., 2023). Meperidine is identical to the morphine acts, primarily targeting the central nervous system. At the same time, meperidine stimulates the μ -opioid receptors involved in analgesia, whereas opioid dependence correlates with the delta receptors. Meperidine has side effects, including mood disturbances, sedation, respiratory depression in newborns, nausea and vomiting (Thigpen, Odle, & Harirforoosh, 2019; Wexler, 2005). Like other opioids, meperidine is metabolized in the liver to its major metabolite, meperidinic acid and only about 20% undergoes conjugation with glucuronic acid. It is also metabolised by N-demethylation to form normeperidine and this is followed by hydrolysis and partial conjugation. Normeperidine is more potent and is approximately 50% less active than meperidine and therefore possesses twice as much activity in the CNS (Agirregoitia, et al., 2006). Researchers have shown that exposure to opioids in adult males suppresses hormone production from the hypothalamus, pituitary gland, adrenal gland, and gonads. These findings occurred in individuals who developed lower blood levels of gonadotropins, cortisol, and testosterone within hours of acute ingestion. This syndrome is caused by opioids and results in hypogonadism (Déglon, Martin, & Imer, 2004; Duca, et al., 2019). Some studies have shown that long-term administration of opioid use has adverse effects on sperm motility, morphology and causes increased damage to DNA in spermatozoa in male animals. Exposure to opioids causes oxidative stress which plays an important role in the causes of increased DNA fragmentation and male infertility (Barenys, et al., 2009). Moreover, some studies have indicated that the dangerous effect of opioids causes reproductive dysfunction in males and females and may

endanger pregnancy (Flannagan, et al., 2020; Vuong, et al., 2010). Therefore, this study investigated to determine the impact role of meperidine in sexual function and pregnancy of mice in males and females.

Materials and Methods

Forty males and females of Swiss albino mice were gained from an animal house of the Technical Institute in Kut city, aged (10) weeks. The animals were kept in cages and left (14) days before the experiment and maintained at room temperature (21-25 C). The light (12 h light; 12h dark). The body weight of its animal is about (26-33 g). The animals were fed with pellets and water by ad libitum. After 14 days, the animals were left for mating (one male + three females) in every cage. The experiment was designed by distributing the animals into two groups.: T1, the control animals (n=20: male and female) were injected (1ml /day) distilled water intramuscularly, T2: the meperidine treatment (n=20: male and female) were injected (25mg/kg/day) (Zhang, et al., 2014). All the treatments for animals were persistent for 77 days without interruption. After 11 weeks, the blood samples were collected in a dry tube for serum separation and preserved at -20°C to analyse reproductive hormone levels (prolactin, testosterone, LH and FSH). All animals were euthanasia (cervical dislocation) and histological sections of ovaries, uterus and testis were sectioned and preserved in 10% formalin (pH 7.4) for examination.

Statistical Analysis

All research data were recorded according to the GraphPad Prism 9.2.1 used to gather, summarize, analyze and present data. The data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant, while P-values equal to or less than 0.001 were considered highly significant and then a comparison was made with two autonomous groups using the independent t-test.

Results

The results in Figure 1 shows the results of the hormonal analysis of female mice, which showed that the average levels of LH and FSH in the treated group showed a very significant decrease

compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$) and the average levels of estrogen and progesterone in the treated group also showed significant decreases compared to the control group ($p < 0.01$).

Figure 1. Comparison of Mean Female Mice between the Control Group and the Treated Group Based on Different Sex Hormones Showed a Significant Difference.

Note: * $P < 0.1$, and *** $P < 0.001$)

The hormonal assay of male mice showed that the mean prolactin level in the treated group was highly significantly increased compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$), while the mean

testosterone, LH, and FSH levels in the treated group showed there is a significant decrease when compared to the control group ($p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.1$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Comparison of Mean Male Mice between the Control Group and the Treated Group Based on Different Sex Hormones Showed a Significant Difference

Note: * $P < 0.1$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$

The average number of follicles in the treated group showed a significant decrease from the average of the control group (14.9 ± 2.85) versus (20.50 ± 1.36) respectively ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1). The average number of follicles in the treated group showed a significant decrease from the average of the control group (14.9 ± 2.85) versus (20.50 ± 1.36) respectively ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1).

Table 2 demonstrates that the mean body weight in the treated group showed a significant decrease compared to the mean of the control group (21.01 ± 1.26) versus (27.55 ± 0.41), respectively ($p < 0.001$). Figure 3 showed that the proportion of females in the treated group was higher than that of males: 15 (75%) females versus 5 (25%) males.

Table 1. Comparison between Two Study Groups Regarding the Follicles

No of follicles	Control	Treated	P
Range	19-23	11-21	p<0.001
Mean \pm SD	20.50 \pm 1.36	14.9 \pm 2.85	

Note: P: probability value; SD: standard deviation

Table 2. Comparison between Two Study Groups Regarding Body Weight

Body weight	Control	Treated	P
Range	26.9-28.3	19.5-27.3	p<0.001
Mean \pm SD	27.55 \pm 0.41	21.01 \pm 1.26	

Note: P: probability value; SD: standard deviation

Figure 3. Pie Chart Showing Frequency Distribution in Treated Mice Enrolled in the Current Study

Discussion

Meperidine is a narcotic drug used widely for women's labour (Tennese, & Wevrick, 2011). The experimental result of this study indicated in Figure 1 that the hormonal analysis of female mice showed the average levels of LH and FSH in the treated group with very significant decrease compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$) and the average levels of estrogen and progesterone in the treated group also showed

slightly decreases compared to the control group ($p < 0.01$), these results attributed to hypothalamus's major role in secreting luteinizing hormone-releasing hormone (LHRH), which leads to partial changes in luteinizing hormone, follicle-stimulating hormone and other hormones. The results of Figure 1 agree with the result of a study conducted by AL-Shemary (2018), which proved a significant decrease in the level of (FSH and LH) hormones after administration of tramadol.

Some researchers have found that one of the major opioid alkaloids or opioid peptides causes disturbances in the neuroendocrine secretion and hormone regulation of the anterior pituitary gland, especially the secretion of luteinising hormone and this agrees with our study (Böttcher, et al., 2017; Fountas, Van Uum, & Karavitaki, 2020). The present study showed that the results of Table 1 the average number of follicles in the treated group showed a significant decrease compared to the control animal group may be because the use of meperidine as pain relief may affect hormonal balance and changes in tissues of the ovary and uterus as Figure 4 and 5, but if it leads to alterations in activity or stress

hormone levels it may negatively affect follicle growth. This agrees with Elhomosany (2021), who reported that the total number of follicles, LH, FSH, estrogen and progesterone were significantly lower in the tramadol-treated group. Some opioids cause inhibition of potassium chloride which leads to inducing myometrium contractility as tramadol and this is noted in our uterus histological results Figure 4 as increasing number of inflammatory cells, the endometrial lining appears thinner, indicating atroph and stroma because estradiol is responsible for increasing cell density and stimulating uterine cell proliferation (Rathod, et al., 2021).

Figure 4. The Uterine Section Shows (A) Control Group in Mice Showing the Structure of Characterized (Normal Stoma (S) and Endometrium Glands (EG). (B) and (C) Section for Treated Group: Hypertrophied endometrial Glands (HEG), Stoma: , Increasing Number Inflammatory Cells with Endometrial Lining would Appear Thinner than normal, indicating Atrophy

Figure 5. A: Ovary Histological Section (Control Group) in Mice Showing (Growth Secondary Follicles (SF) and Corpus Luteum (CL)). B: Histopathological Findings of the Ovary Revealed Congestion with a Reduction in the Number of Ovarian Follicles, increased Number of Small Arterioles Follicles, Damage in Development of Follicular, Cyst Formation and Hypercellularity of the Ovarian Stoma . (40x10) (H&E)

The results of the tissue section showed a clear change in the form of a decrease in the number of ovarian follicles, an increase in the number of small arterial follicles, hypercellularity and cyst formation. These results causes appeared ovarian dysfunction in females and problems in the reproductive system. Ovarian dysfunction was manifested in cell degeneration in the form of atrophy and a decrease in the secretory function of the endometrial glands Figure 5. These results of our study are in agreement with the results of recent studies conducted by Ahmed and Karkar (2014) which have suggested that rats received subcutaneous injections of tramadol (40 mg/kg body weight) as an opioid analgesic, for 8 weeks were found to increase in the follicle-stimulating hormone because decreased in the levels of luteinizing hormone in plasma. Farag et al (2018) suggested that long-term treatment with opiates may cause disturbance in sperm motility, morphology and increased average of DNA damage in spermatozoa in male mice. These results agree with our study in Figure 2 that explained a

significant decrease in testosterone may be because of destroyed Sertoli cells resulting in meperidine consumption (de Vries, et al., 2020; Jafarpour Fard, Karami, & Jalali Nadoushan, 2019). This decrease in the level of testosterone hormone could lead also to an increase in the FSH level as a negative feedback effect which could cause an increase in LH and prolactin levels, these results were similar to the results of Alshammary, et al (2020) that the observation which reported increasing in estradiol and prolactin levels and decreasing in the testosterone, luteinizing hormone and follicular stimulating hormone levels after tramadol administration. The Microscopical examination of testicular biopsy in Figure 6 showed low-grade inflammatory cell infiltration and germ cell degeneration along with the shattered pattern of the seminiferous epithelium and atrophy of the seminiferous tubules that caused chronic inflammation and systemic diseases or hormonal deficiency because the disorders in the endocrine and paracrine functions which happen due to altered LH, somatotropin and somatostatin.

Figure 6. (A) Micrograph of Tissue Sections from Testis (Control Group) Showing Seminiferous Tubules (ST): They Appear Normal, Showing a Well-Defined Structure with Rounded Outlines and Normal Arrangement of Sperm Cells (S). (B): The Section Illustrates Notable Pathological Changes in the Testicular Structure Compared to Control Groups. The Seminiferous Tubules Show Signs of Atrophy, Characterized by Thinning of the Tubular Wall with a Decreased Diameter and Some Tubules May Exhibit an Irregularly Shaped. Reduce the Number of Spermatogonia Cells and the Presence and Infiltration of Inflammatory Cells in the Interstitial Spaces between the Seminiferous Tubules (H&E).

As well as meperidine causes a decrease in the level of testosterone, prolactin and gonadotropin-releasing hormone that affects the hypothalamus or pituitary glands, causing dysfunction of the secondary sex organs (Al-Shemary, 2018; Abbas, Kadhim, & Abed, 2023). Some studies showed the causes of these changes may attributed to the destruction of Sertoli cells and sperms contain abundant polyunsaturated fatty acids in their plasma membranes which undergo lipid peroxidation because alteration level of hormones induced by opioid drugs (Cota, et al., 2006; Sayed, & Zidan, 2016). Many researchers indicated that the use of drugs derived from opiates may lead to hypogonadism, primarily due to reduced gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) and testosterone (Rathod, et al., 2021). Male mice's sexual behaviour may change by using opiates, which results in lower desire and mating success (Pfaus, & Gorzalka, 1987). The changes in male behaviour might occur due to hormonal alteration and opioid-induced central nervous system effects (Siddiqui, et al., 1995). Table 2 showed a significant decrease in the body weight of the mice treatment group after intake of meperidine for 70 days and this is similar to morphine effect (Doyle, et al., 2017). This disagrees with some studies that suggest the use of opioids can not affect on body white as Ahmed & Kurkar (2014). Some studies found that opioid drugs affect the hypothalamus which causes loss of appetite and energy regulation for that reason, the continued use of opioids can affect body weight (Kingsberg, Clayton, & Pfaus, 2015). Cota et al (2006), Valbron and Zvonarev (2020) referred to the use of many medications, naloxone and naltrexone on some individuals can suppress their food intake and also reported decreased hunger. Ma et al (2006) suggested that a single opioid receptor plays an important role in the regulation of feeding, the μ -opioid receptor. Some research has shown that ameliorative food intake has an important role in imbalanced changes in appetite that affect opioid receptors (Kadhim, 2024; Abed, Abd, & Abd, 2018).

Conclusion

Some research has found that one of the major opioid alkaloids or opioid peptides causes disturbances in the neuroendocrine secretion and hormone regulation of the anterior pituitary gland, especially the secretion of luteinising hormone (Wylot, Tworús, & Okrasa, 2013). Most animal studies have confirmed that opioids produce a greater degree of analgesia in male rodents than in female rodents as shown in our study results in Figure (3), this agreement with Xu, et al (2024), but disagrees with Lopresti and Esguerra (2020) because female mice undergo cyclical changes in hormones that may make the female reproductive system more sensitive to drugs than the male reproductive system, Meperidine may act differently on female neurotransmitter systems, insofar as these systems may regulate hormone release and be involved in controlling reproductive behaviour by regulating the release of dopamine and serotonin by opioids associated with reproductive functions and direct impacts on ovarian function (Kaminski, 2004). In summary, the results of the present study proved and demonstrated that meperidine as a drug analgesic has an important role on fertility in female mice contrast to male mice and body weight. The alteration and imbalance of increased expression of opioid receptors, direct influence on the work of the ovarian, behavioural influences, altered neurotransmitter interactions and pharmacokinetic variances are all possible explanations for these effects.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research of Iraq, Middle Technical University and Kut Technical Institute.

Funding statement

We appreciate the support of the Ministry of Higher Education and scientific Research, Republic of Iraq, which funded this study through the continuous support of Middle Technical University, Kut Technical Institute.

Approval

There is no special approval need to perform this study

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest in this study.

Author's Contribution

R. A., D.M., and K.H.Y. were responsible for the experiment design and data analysis and carried out all of the experiments and drafted the manuscript; D.M and M.A participated in the evaluation of each experiment; R. A., D.M. K.H.Y and M.A revised the paper and provided technical support and the final edition of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

References

Abbas, D. M., Kadhim, R. A., & Abed, S. N. (2023). The effect of acesulfame-K and aspartame as sweetener materials in food products on body parameters of rats. *Journal of Population Therapeutics and Clinical Pharmacology*, 30(5), 607–614. <https://doi.org/10.53555/jptcp.v30i5.3570>

Abed, Q. J. O., Abd, S. N., & Abd, R. K. (2018). Effect of complications of contraceptives used for long periods on women in Bant Al-Huda Teaching Hospital at Al-Nasiriya city. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 10(2), 319–322.

Agirregoitia, E., Valdivia, A., Carracedo, A., Casis, L., Gil, J., Subirán, N., Ochoa, C., & Irazusta, J. (2006). Expression and localization of δ -, κ -, and μ -opioid receptors in human spermatozoa and implications for sperm motility. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 91(12), 4969–4975. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2006-0961>

Ahmed, M. A., & Kurkar, A. (2014). Effects of opioid (tramadol) treatment on testicular functions in adult male rats: The role of nitric oxide and oxidative stress. *Clinical and Experimental Pharmacology and Physiology*, 41(4),

317–323. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1440-1681.12222>

Alshammary, A. G., Abbas, R. N., Jouda, J., & Jumaa, M. S. (2020). Effect of different concentrations of tramadol on testes and male hormones in young and adult mice. *Annals of Tropical Medicine and Health*, 23, 231–386. <https://doi.org/10.36295/ASRO.2020.231386>

Al-Shemary, N. N. (2018). The histological and hormonal changes that occur on reproductive system and pregnancy in adult albino mice after treatment of tramadol. *Journal of Wasit for Science and Medicine*, 11(1), 200–208.

Barenys, M., Macià, N., Camps, L., de Lapuente, J., Gomez-Catalan, J., Gonzalez-Linares, J., Borràs, M., Rodamilans, M., & Llobet, J. M. (2009). Chronic exposure to MDMA (ecstasy) increases DNA damage in sperm and alters testes histopathology in male rats. *Toxicology Letters*, 191(1), 40–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2009.08.002>

Böttcher, B., Seeber, B., Leyendecker, G., & Wildt, L. (2017). Impact of the opioid system on the reproductive axis. *Fertility and Sterility*, 108(2), 207–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fertnstert.2017.06.026>

Cota, D., Tschöp, M. H., Horvath, T. L., & Levine, A. S. (2006). Cannabinoids, opioids and eating behaviour: The molecular face of hedonism? *Brain Research Reviews*, 51(1), 85–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresrev.2005.11.004>

de Vries, F., Bruin, M., Lobatto, D. J., Dekkers, O. M., Schoones, J. W., van Furth, W. R., Pereira, A. M., Karavitaki, N., Biermasz, N. R., & Zamanipour Najafabadi, A. H. (2020). Opioids and their endocrine effects: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 105(4), 1020–1029. <https://doi.org/10.1210/clinem/dgz022>

- Déglon, J.-J., Martin, J.-L., & Imer, R.-L. (2004). Methadone patients' sexual dysfunctions: Clinical and treatment issues. *Heroin Addiction & Related Clinical Problems*, 6(3), 17–26.
- Doyle, H. H., Eidson, L. N., Sinkiewicz, D. M., & Murphy, A. Z. (2017). Sex differences in microglia activity within the periaqueductal gray of the rat: A potential mechanism driving the dimorphic effects of morphine. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 37(12), 3202–3214. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2906-16.2017>
- Duca, Y., Aversa, A., Condorelli, R. A., Calogero, A. E., & La Vignera, S. (2019). Substance abuse and male hypogonadism. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 8(5), 732. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm8050732>
- Elhomosany, N. M. (2021). Effect of tramadol on the ovaries of female mice. *Egyptian Journal of Histology*, 44(3), 805–813. https://doi.org/10.4103/ejh.ejh_25_21
- Farag, A. G., Basha, M. A., Amin, S. A., Elnaidany, N. F., Elhelbawy, N. G., Mostafa, M. M., Khodier, S. A., Ibrahim, R. A., & Mahfouz, R. Z. (2018). Tramadol (opioid) abuse is associated with a dose- and time-dependent poor sperm quality and hyperprolactinaemia in young men. *Andrologia*, 50(6), e13026. <https://doi.org/10.1111/and.13026>
- Flannagan, K. S., Sjaarda, L. A., Mumford, S. L., & Schisterman, E. F. (2020). Prescription opioid use among populations of reproductive age: Effects on fertility, pregnancy loss, and pregnancy complications. *Epidemiologic Reviews*, 42(1), 117–133. <https://doi.org/10.1093/epirev/mxaa004>
- Fountas, A., Van Uum, S., & Karavitaki, N. (2020). Opioid-induced endocrinopathies. *The Lancet Diabetes & Endocrinology*, 8(1), 68–80. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-8587\(19\)30240-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-8587(19)30240-9)
- Jafarpour Fard, M., Karami, M., & Jalali Nadoushan, M. (2019). Interaction of sulphiride with morphine in induction of male rat infertility. *Journal of Basic and Clinical Pathophysiology*, 7(2), 6–11.
- Kadhim, R. A. (2024). Ameliorative role of *Nigella sativa* seeds and levamisole on the immune response of adult male rabbits. *Diyala Journal for Veterinary Sciences*, 2(3), 98–112.
- Kaminski, T. (2004). The response of phospholipase C/protein kinase C and adenylyl cyclase/protein kinase A pathways in porcine theca interna cells to opioid agonist FK 33-824. *Domestic Animal Endocrinology*, 27(4), 379–396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.domaniend.2004.06.001>
- Kingsberg, S. A., Clayton, A. H., & Pfaus, J. G. (2015). The female sexual response: Current models, neurobiological underpinnings and agents currently approved or under investigation for the treatment of hypoactive sexual desire disorder. *CNS Drugs*, 29(11), 915–933. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40263-015-0282-3>
- Lopresti, N. M., Esguerra, M., & Mermelstein, P. G. (2020). Sex differences in animal models of opioid reward. *Current Sexual Health Reports*, 12, 186–194. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11930-020-00265-3>
- Ma, J., Zhang, Y., Kalyuzhny, A. E., & Pan, Z.-Z. (2006). Emergence of functional δ -opioid receptors induced by long-term treatment with morphine. *Molecular Pharmacology*, 69(4), 1137–1145. <https://doi.org/10.1124/mol.105.019877>
- Pfaus, J. G., & Gorzalka, B. B. (1987). Opioids and sexual behaviour. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 11(1), 1–34. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-7634\(87\)80002-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-7634(87)80002-7)
- Rathod, G., Patil, S. R., Ahmed, M. L., & Vijaykumar, K. (2021). Tramadol induced ovarian and uterine changes in albino rats. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*, 33(51B), 212–217. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jpri/2021/v33i51B33508>

- Sayed, H. Y., & Zidan, A. H. (2016). Histopathological and biochemical effects of acute and chronic tramadol drug toxicity on liver, kidney, and testicular function in adult male albino rats. *Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 1(2), 41–49.
- Siddiqui, A., Haq, S., Shaharyar, S., & Haider, S. G. (1995). Morphine induces reproductive changes in female rats and their male offspring. *Reproductive Toxicology*, 9(2), 143–151. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0890-6238\(94\)00074-M](https://doi.org/10.1016/0890-6238(94)00074-M)
- Tennese, A. A., & Wevrick, R. (2011). Impaired hypothalamic regulation of endocrine function and delayed counterregulatory response to hypoglycemia in *Magel2*-null mice. *Endocrinology*, 152(3), 967–978. <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.2010-0908>
- Thigpen, J. C., Odle, B. L., & Harirforoosh, S. (2019). Opioids: A review of pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics in neonates, infants, and children. *European Journal of Drug Metabolism and Pharmacokinetics*, 44, 591–609. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13318-019-00564-5>
- Valbrun, L. P., & Zvonarev, V. (2020). The opioid system and food intake: Use of opiate antagonists in the treatment of binge eating disorder and abnormal eating behaviour. *Journal of Clinical Medicine Research*, 12(2), 41–46. <https://doi.org/10.14740/jocmr4071>
- Vuong, C., Van Uum, S. H. M., O'Dell, L. E., Lutfy, K., & Friedman, T. C. (2010). The effects of opioids and opioid analogs on animal and human endocrine systems. *Endocrine Reviews*, 31(1), 98–132. <https://doi.org/10.1210/er.2009-0009>
- Wexler, P. (Ed.). (2005). *Encyclopedia of toxicology* (2nd ed.). Academic Press.
- Wylot, B., Tworusi, K., & Okrasa, S. (2013). The effects of μ -, δ - and κ -opioid receptor activation on luteinizing and follicle-stimulating hormone secretion from porcine pituitary cells. *Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, 64(4), 505–511.
- Xu, Q., Jin, L., Wang, L., Tang, Y., Wu, H., Chen, Q., & Sun, L. (2024). The role of gonadal hormones in regulating opioid antinociception. *Annals of Medicine*, 56(1), 2329259. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07853890.2024.2329259>
- Yilmaz, M., Suleyman, B., Mammadov, R., Altuner, D., Bulut, S., & Suleyman, H. (2023). The role of adrenaline, noradrenaline, and cortisol in the pathogenesis of the analgesic potency, duration, and neurotoxic effect of meperidine. *Medicina*, 59(10), 1793. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina59101793>
- Zhang, C., Yu, Z., Li, X., Xu, Y., & Liu, D. (2014). Chronopharmacodynamics and chronopharmacokinetics of pethidine in mice. *PLOS ONE*, 9(7), e102054. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0102054>